

MINERAL WATERS SUITABLE FOR BALNEOTHERAPY OF DERMATOLOGICAL PROBLEMS IN BULGARIA

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ABSTRACT: *On the territory of Bulgaria, 207 springs and water wells with total discharge over 1366 l/s are certified for balneotherapy by the Ministry of Health. When characterised and mapped for balneotherapy of dermatologic diseases, concentrations of hydrogen sulphide and sulphates are primarily taken into account. High concentrations of H₂S and SO₄²⁻ are observed in the Low Danubian Artesian region and on the east border of the Rila – Rhodope and Intermediate regions. With higher concentrations of hydrogen sulfide there are 13 water sources and with sulfates are 46. From these sources of mineral water six have a high value of both sulfuric components. These are “Obedinenie”, “Voneshtavoda” and four sources from the “Haskovskimineralni bani” aquifer. The geological – hydrogeological features of certified mineral waters are revised in this article.*

Keywords: *mineral waters, dermatological diseases, sulfates, hydrogen sulfide, Bulgaria*

INTRODUCTION

Mineral waters are well known for their auspicious healing properties for different types of diseases. Since ancient times, people have taken advantage of those properties and made specific resorts for their time. On the territory of the Republic of Bulgaria, the exploitation recourse of mineral waters by Hristov et al. (2019) amounts to 4600 l/s total discharge, but only 30 % of it is being used. By the end of the year 2023, 1366 l / s of these resources are certified by the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Bulgaria. They are divided between 207 natural springs and wells with water yields for balneological purposes with healing properties for dermatological diseases.

It should be noted that in Bulgaria the term “Mineral water” is used for deep ground – water whose temperature, chemical components and physical properties do not alter with climate, nor any other change in nature (Ordinance 14). This means that both cold waters and thermal ones (over 20 °C) are included in this research. There are also no minimum nor maximum concentrations for any element for the water to be considered mineral. For a source to be considered curative water it goes through complex evaluation, that does not separate different components to assess its value as such.

Most of the aquifers were well explored in the 1960s and 1970s of the XX century by Shterev (1964), Petrov et al. (1970) and others. The aquifers are located mostly in the southern part of the country from Stara Planina. Here the Alpo-Himalaian orogeny creates favourable conditions for the formation of substantial amounts of deep groundwaters. In the north, part of the Moesian platform, the water sources are connected to deep aquifers, reached by exploratory wells for oil and gas.

The number of studies by Carubbi et al. (2013), Carbajo et al. (2017), Coavoy-Sanchez et al. (2019), Cacciapuoti et al. (2020) and Sokrateva (2020) state that sulfur and more specifically hydrogen sulfide (H₂S), predominantly found in gaseous state, help with the treatment of different dermatological diseases, with its anti-inflammatory and antibacterial and exfoliating properties. The current objective of this article is to define, characterise and classify mineral waters, approved by the Ministry of Health for therapeutic effects on skin diseases, and to take note of their sulfuric components.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The balneological certificates issued, until the end of 2023, by the Ministry of Health are used as the main source of information. These certificates give an assessment of the mineral waters on the territory of the country, for the treatment of different health issues. More than 257 groundwater sources are reviewed. From which, 207 are established as suitable for the treatment of dermatological diseases. Most of the stations are without coordinates. To solve this, information from mapping materials, tables of different articles and coordinates of near stations were used. Each probe is given a number in advance for easier use in the following steps of the research.

The information from the created database is processed with the GIS (Geographic Information System) programme ArcMap 10.5. A classification of four groups is made by the concentrations of the sulfates in the mineral waters. (Fig. 1)

With GW_Chart a Piper diagram is made, defining the type of the underground waters (Fig. 2). The combination of different methods allows for faster and more precise data analysing.

Figure 1. Hydrogeological mapping (by Iovchev and Altovskij 1975) of mineral water sources and their SO_4^{2-} concentrations in mg/l

Figure 2. Piper diagram of mineral waters with TDS concentrations in mg/l

RESULTS

Samples were selected with data of their temperature, mineralisation, H_2S and SO_4^{2-} . The last two components are the main ones by which mineral waters were distributed in the current research. The waters were grouped by the type of rock of their aquifer, the minimum and maximum values of the components aforementioned, and the number of water-yielding sources (NWS) for better and more accurate data analysis (Table 1).

Table 1. Table of the water-bearing rocks, number of water-producing sources, and the highest and lowest values of the researched components.

Type of rocks	T min [°C]	T max [°C]	TDS min [mg/l]	TDS max [mg/l]	H ₂ S min [mg/l]	H ₂ S max [mg/l]	SO ₄ ²⁻ min [mg/l]	SO ₄ ²⁻ max [mg/l]	NWS [-]
Limestones and sandstones	23	48,9	335	1978	1,52	6,29	20,16	475,3	5
Volcanic	17,7	57,6	118	1690	0,02	344,1	13,99	868,3	21
Gneiss	18,2	88	214,6	2329	0,01	3	27,98	526,7	36
Gneiss and granite	36,9	98	192	636	0,62	20,1	26,54	214,6	10
Granite	25	96,2	218	6496	0,08	101	17,49	1549	53
Granodiorite	23,8	79	184	984	0,04	7,3	24,07	460,7	11
Carbonated rocks	19	68,2	413	10892	0,013	390	15,23	2134	33
Granite, gneiss, marble	33,5	41,8	205	243	0,06	0,42	22,43	32,3	15
Metamorphic	52,5	61,5	523	1015	0,015	6,33	192,2	249,0	5
Marble	21	73,3	325	1715	0,25	1,5	23,34	658,4	6
Marble and gneiss	22	79,3	557	2885	0,25	1,11	26,75	293,8	5
Sandstone and conglomerates	12,8	84,3	226	1115	0,01	309,5	17,08	260,9	7

From the analyses that were done, the following points can be noted about the distribution of mineral water sources, suitable for treatment in dermatological diseases:

In the Low Danubian Artesian Region, the main aquifer of almost all mineral waters is the carbonate rock (limestone and dolomites) of the Malm-Valangian aquifer (Upper Jurassic – Lower Cretaceous), mostly concentrated in the Varna Artesian Basin. Here 31 water sources are located and, despite the low number, they yield over 450 l/s of mineral water, which is close to the amount given from the Rila – Rhodope Region.

The felsic crystalline and metamorphic rocks are the dominant type of mineral water aquifers in the intermediate region. In the Burgas and Sofia regions, the aquifers are predominantly volcanic rocks, while a secondary role is given to the underlying carbonate sedimental rocks. Few terrigenous sedimentary rocks serve as mineral water-bearing units. The 81 sources listed here do not mean high resource usage. The eastern part of the Intermediate region is notoriously poor in mineral waters for dermatology treatment, and the concentration of water sources is in the western part. The entire region gives barely more than 250 l/s of mineral water.

In the Rila – Rhodope region, magmatic and metamorphic rock aquifers (granites, gneiss, and marble) in its central and western parts. There is also a small number of terrigenous aquifers. In the eastern parts of the region, more substantial aquifers are the effusive alkaline-type rocks. The 95 groundwater sources give discharges over 480 l/s, making it the most abundant region of mineral waters suitable for the treatment of skin diseases.

From the results, it can be noted that most of the mineral water aquifers are fractured type. Karst-fractured, mostly dominates the northern parts of the country, and there are few occasions of porous type.

The chemical components of the mineral water sources based on the certificates are mostly SO₄²⁻, HCO₃⁻, Na⁺ and Ca²⁺ (Fig. 2) in different ratios. In the Low Danubian Artesian region the sulfates are partially replaced by Cl⁻. Upon determining the types of water, it is observed that the predominant are HCO₃⁻–SO₄²⁻–Na and SO₄²⁻–HCO₃⁻–Na. As in the research by Hristov et al. (2019), Na⁺ is present in almost all mineral waters, where it is the main cation for determining the type of waters. On very rare occasions, carbonate aquifers Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺ completely replace it. Anions on the other hand constantly change their positions. The most dominant is HCO₃⁻, followed by SO₄²⁻, rarely CO₃²⁻ and Cl⁻.

Mineral waters are characterised by a wide range of temperatures. Values vary from 10^o C to 100^o C. Only five of them cannot be considered thermal waters of which the lowest reported is by the groundwater source “Voneshtavoda” - 12,8^o C. All the others have temperature of outflow over 20^o C and the highest is 98^o C in “Saparevabanya”.

Total water mineralisation (TDS) also varies greatly. The highest value is in 'Krushuna' – 10,89 g/l, and 27 of the groundwater sources have a concentration greater than 1 g/l. The lowest value is from the 'Knyazhevo' aquifer – 118 mg/l.

Regarding the sulphur content, 135 mineral water sources have a hydrogen sulphide less than 1 mg/l, in 13 the values are greater than 10 mg/l, of which in six the value of H₂S is greater than 250 mg/l. The sulfates are above 200 mg/l in 46 sources of mineral water, of which 10 are above 800 mg/l.

DISCUSSION

Mineral waters investigated give a tentative picture of the role sulphur plays in the treatment of dermatological diseases. As H₂S is SO₄²⁻ in unsubstantial amounts in more than half of the investigated water sources, but this does not deny their value. Regarding the thirteen mineral water sources with hydrogen sulphide greater than 10 mg/l, the research of Carubbi et al. (2013), Carbajo et al. (2017), Coavoy-Sanchez et al. (2019), Cacciapuoti et al. (2020) and Sokrateva (2020) states that the chemical compound probably enhances their healing properties against skin diseases. From the same data, we can note that the sulphates in 46 mineral waters should also have an auspicious effect on the recovery of the skin and the anti-inflammatory processes. Mineral waters with higher values of H₂S and SO₄²⁻ are mostly found in the central parts of the Low Danubian Artesian Range and the eastern border between the Rila – Rhodope and Intermediate regions.

Despite the high range of mineralisation and temperatures of the mineral waters, no link was found between their temperature and the concentration of H₂S and SO₄²⁻. The high TDS does not guarantee high concentrations of sulfur components and vice versa. Such examples are the aquifers “Mihalkovo” and “Marash”, where their TDS is above 2500 mg/l, but H₂S is below 1 mg/l, and “Kyustendil” has TDS under 600 mg/l but hydrogen sulphide is above 6 mg/l. Same goes for temperature. The H₂S concentrations in ‘Voneshtavoda’ despite its low temperature are quite high - 309 mg/l, but in ‘Saparevabanya’ it is less than 1 mg/l.

Based on the results, six sources of mineral water are highlighted for their sulfuric components. They could be used for future research to find more details about the role of H₂S and SO₄²⁻ in the treatment of dermatological diseases. These are the mineral waters of the ‘Voneshtavoda’ collected in sandstones and conglomerates, with concentration of H₂S = 309 mg/l and SO₄²⁻ = 260 mg/l, the “Obedinenie” carbonate rock aquifer with concentrations of 390 mg/l and 1476 mg/l respectively and four different underground water sources of the volcanic aquifer ‘Haskovski’ mineralnibani’ volcanic aquifer with hydrogen sulphide concentrations of 336 mg/l, 265 mg/l, 344 mg/l and 320 mg/l and sulphate concentrations above 800 mg/l.

CONCLUSION

Thirteen water sources with high concentrations of H₂S and 46 with SO₄²⁻ are expected to have higher healing factors against dermatological problems. For future investigation of sulphur and its healing properties, six sources with high values of hydrogen sulphide and sulphate are highlighted: aquifers ‘Voneshtavoda’, ‘Obedinenie’ and ‘Haskovski mineralnibani’.

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